

Facile Fabrication of Flame-retardant Graphene/Sponge Composite for Pressure Sensing and Electromagnetic Interference Shielding

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Polyurethane foam (PUF)

Unique properties

- ☐ Comfortable
- ☐ Lightweight
- ☐ Good resilience
- ☐ Insulating behaviour

Advanced applications

☐ Smart foams (e-foams), i.e., EMI shielding, TENG, piezoresistive, supercapacitors, thermal energy conversion, catalysis, etc.

EMI shielding

Advanced applications

Piezoresistive sensor

Steam generation

Supercapacitors

Energy conversion

Catalysis

Issues with neat PUF

Highly flammable

- PUF mainly contains C and H
- It is highly porous → swift transfer of heat and fuel during fire hazard

Spreads fire to nearby materials

- Drips flammable molten polymer

Releases toxic and dense smokes

- CO, HCN → deadly within minutes
- Dense smokes makes evacuation and firefighting difficult

Fire risks of consumer products: furniture, cars

Needs modification to lower the flammability and impart functionality

Current strategies

i) Addition of fillers during fabrication

- Needs high loading
- Affects the physical properties of PUF

ii) Surface coating (Post treatment)

- Modification is on the surface with minimal impact on properties
- Expensive, time-consuming, and tedious due to extensive manual operations

H. Yang et al./Composites Part B 176 (2019) 107185

Research interests

- 2D layered nanofillers
graphene, clay

- 3D fillers, graphite (EG)

- 0D nanofillers, CB

- Multifunctional thin film coating applications

Polymer Nanocomposites

Nano Thin Film Coatings

Materials Characterization

- Layer-by-layer (LbL) self-assembly

- Microimaging (TEM, SEM, AFM)

- Thermal (TGA, DSC)
- X-ray (SAXS, XRD)
- Thin film (ellipsometry, UV-vis, FT-IR, QCM)
- Flame retardancy (UL-94, MCC, CC)

Research interests ... cont.

Nanocomposites

PUF/EG/CB/IL^[1]

- Excellent flame retardancy
- Application in energy harvesting
- Application in oil-leak sensor

Functional coatings

LbL, PEC, dip-coating^[2-4]

- Improved flame retardancy
- Application in pressure sensing and energy
- Application in EMI shielding

Matrices & fillers

Matrices: Several biopolymers (CH, AL, PDL, PA)

- Carbon based fillers: expandable graphite (EG), GNP, CB, biomass-derived mesoporous carbon
- Clay: montmorillonite (MMT)

Non-flammable

Energy harvesting

Motion sensing

EMI shielding

[1] T. G. Weldemhret et al. /Chemical Engineering Journal 450 (2022) 137982

[2] T.G. Weldemhret et al. /Progress in Organic Coatings 161 (2021) 106480

[3] T. G. Weldemhret et al. /ACS Appl. Nano Mater. 2022, 5, 9, 12464–12476

[4] T. G. Weldemhret et al. /Adv. Mat. Inter. 2023, (in press)

GNP/PUF composite fabrication process

PUF fabrication (A) and coating process (B)

Solvent recycling and recovery (A, B)

Coating characterization

Digital images of neat and coated PUF

SEM images of (A) neat and (B) coated PUF

Water stability of the coatings

FR properties: MCC and CC tests

Fig. (A) MCC HRR curve, (B) CC HRR curve, (C) ARHE, (D) THR, (E) RSR, (F) TSR, (G) TSP, (H) CO₂P, and (I) COP. The average value was used for plotting all curves (n = 2).

Piezoresistivity: Qualitative evaluation

Video. A circuit constructed with the GNP@PUF foam, revealing the brightness of LED changes with the compression/stretching and release of the conductive GNP@PUF.

Piezoresistivity: Quantitative evaluation

Fig. (A) Experimental setup for the pressure sensor characterization. Schematic showing the circuit diagram of GNP@PUF under (B) compressive and (C) stretching mode. (D) Key performance evaluation

Fig. Schematic illustration of the sensing mechanism of the GNP@PUF sensor under compression and stretching sensing modes.

Sensor characterization

Fig. (A) The GNP@PUF pressure sensor, (B) Sensor response vs. strain, (C) correlation between resistance and strain, (D) calculated gauge factor for different compressive strains, and (E) correlation between resistance and pressure under compressive mode. (F-J) correlation between resistance and strain under stretching mode.

Sensor response time and durability

Fig. (A) Response time and (B) stability of the pressure sensor.

Human motion monitoring

Fig. Monitoring of various human motions using the GNP@PUF sensor.

Application in EMI shielding

D

(i) Coefficients of shielding mechanism

$$R = \frac{P_{ref}}{P_i} = |S_{11}|^2 = |S_{22}|^2$$

$$T = \frac{P_t}{P_i} = |S_{12}|^2 = |S_{21}|^2$$

$$A = \frac{P_{abs}}{P_i} = 1 - R - T$$

(ii) EMI shielding effectiveness (SE)

$$SE_{ref} = -10 \log\left(\frac{1}{1-R}\right)$$

$$SE_{abs} = -10 \log\left(\frac{1-R}{T}\right)$$

$$SE_{total} = 10 \log\left(\frac{P_i}{P_t}\right) = SE_{ref} + SE_{abs}$$

Fig. (A, B) Experimental setup for EMI shielding measurements: vector network analyzer with the waveguide. (C) EMI shielding mechanism of the foam. (D) Key parameters for evaluating the EMI shielding performance of the foam.

EMI shielding performance

Fig. EMI shielding performance of the foams at a frequency range of 8-12.5 GHz. (A) SE total, (B) effect of thickness, (C) SE reflection, and (D) SE absorption for GNP@PUF.

Conclusions

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